

Assessment of catenary condition monitoring by means of pantograph head acceleration and Artificial Neural Networks

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Abstract

Measuring the pantograph-catenary interaction force is crucial for homologation and maintenance purposes. However, this is an intricate procedure that requires a specially-instrumented pantograph. As an alternative to the traditional method of measuring the interaction force, we propose in this paper a new procedure to predict the current collection quality (usually quantified by the standard deviation of the interaction force) from the vertical acceleration measurements of the pantograph collector head.

The proposed approach consists of properly preprocessing the acceleration signals to train and validate Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) to predict the standard deviation of the interaction force. First, the proposed method is defined with academic examples in which different ANNs identify dropper defects and severe contact wire wear from numerically generated pantograph accelerations. The normalisation of the input data and proper resampling to make samples independent of the train speed are revealed as key aspects in the success of the proposed approach.

Also from a numerical point of view, the method is then applied to predict the standard deviation of the contact force. The results obtained show that these predictions have an error of less than a 10%. The analyses of other potential scenarios such as different train operating speed ranges and the use of displacements instead of acceleration as input, show a poor generalization power of the ANNs used. They provide accurate results only when fed with input samples with the same features as those used in the training stage.

Finally, the proposed approach is applied to the experimental data obtained from a pantograph lab test bench. In this case, the ANNs are able to predict the current collection quality with less than a 10% error in almost 95% of the cases. This work aimed to be an intermediate step between pure numerical analysis and real data measured on track.

Keywords: Artificial Neural Network, condition monitoring, catenary, pantograph, interaction force.

1. Introduction

The overhead contact line, commonly known as the railway catenary (see Figure 1(a)), is a cable structure that provides the locomotive with electrical current through a sliding contact with the pantograph (see Figure 1(b)) on the roof of the traction unit. As catenaries are usually designed for decades of service life [1] during which their reliability must be guaranteed for safe and stable operation, it is important for the catenary operator to have inspection and monitoring systems in place that allow efficient and effective scheduling of maintenance operations. Traditionally, this task is carried out by inspection vehicles with specially-instrumented pantographs, which can mean interrupting regular services. Monitoring the condition of the whole pantograph-catenary system to avoid the use of these dedicated train units has now become a hot topic in research.

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Figure 1: (a) High-speed stitched railway catenary and (b) DSA-380 pantograph.

In other studies, [2] proposed a strategy for monitoring the position and severity of the damage on the catenary masts based on an eigenfrequency-based Bayesian approach, while mast inclination was also included in [3]. Cantilever health monitoring approaches have also been proposed by detecting their components from images and Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCCN) [4, 5]. Images of the cantilevers can also be used to detect loose fasteners, as proposed in [6], with the aid of reinforcement learning techniques, and to detect steady arms slope [7]. Video and thermal images of the pantograph were combined in [8] to detect normal, wear, and defective status using a fuzzy classifier.

Most attention is now being given to catenary health monitoring and fault detection. Several works propose methods for tracking the pantograph-catenary contact point while diagnosing vertical and lateral irregularities of the contact wire from images obtained by cameras located on the locomotive roof [9–13], although these proposals require relatively complicate and expensive equipment. Other proposals [14, 15] infer the system’s performance from a wide set of measurements, such as stagger, contact wire height, pan-head acceleration and pantograph-catenary contact force, which are obtained by a dedicated inspection vehicle.

Wear on the sliding surfaces is one of the main reasons for replacing the contact wire and the pantograph contact strips, so that proper wear monitoring is useful for planning predictive maintenance strategies, although measuring the wear on the contact wire needs specific systems [16]. Some works propose strategies to predict the wear on the pantograph contact strips from images [17] and contact wire wear [18] by training an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) with measurements of contact wire height, stagger and interaction force, among others. However, these approaches need sophisticated measuring instrumentation whose installation in a conventional train implies certain difficulties.

The current collection quality, usually quantified by contact force statistics, is also a parameter that needs to be monitored to guarantee safe operations and detect potentially hazardous sections. High contact force values accelerate contact wire wear while low interaction force may lead to contact losses and electrical arcs, which worsen the power supply and aggravate wear on the sliding surfaces. Some of the approaches in the literature for automatic arc detection [19, 20] are mainly based on acquiring images and applying artificial intelligence tools.

On the other hand, the pantograph-catenary interaction force can be directly measured [21, 22] following the procedure in EN-50317 [23], which is an intricate procedure that cannot be carried out with a conventional pantograph but requires a specially instrumented pantograph. This interaction force can also be estimated by means of indirect measurements on the pantograph. In [24], the authors propose using pantograph collector deformation to obtain the contact force. An Extended Kalman Filter with displacement and velocity measures on the pantograph is used in [25] to estimate the contact force and detect installation errors. Using panhead acceleration seems to be the best approach to estimate the pantograph-catenary contact force since both magnitudes are directly related and they provide an easy low-cost solution that can be implemented on a conventional train [26, 27]. In [27] the authors describe an entire measurement setup to acquire pantograph collector accelerations from optical accelerometers and detect local and distributed defects on the catenary by the Root Mean Square (RMS) value of the acceleration over a moving window of different length.

The present work is mainly aimed at assessing the viability of using the pantograph collector’s vertical acceleration

to estimate the standard deviation of the pantograph-catenary interaction force by ANNs. To this end, we first defined the proposed approach by means of academic examples in which the pantograph acceleration signals were obtained from numerical simulations. The ANNs were then applied to practical problems of increasing difficulty, such as identifying the presence of slackened or broken droppers, detecting severe contact wire wear and predicting the contact force maximum, minimum and standard deviation. Finally, the proposed method was tested in an experimental environment, in which an ANN was trained and tested with acceleration measures of the DSA-380 pantograph on the test bench described in [28]. The proposed method combines the simplicity and low-cost measurements of pantograph collector acceleration and the multi-purpose framework of artificial intelligence techniques in assessing fault detection and current collection quality. We aimed to establish the bases of a method that can be used with on-track measurements to optimize maintenance schedules, reduce downtime and improve safety.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: the procedure followed to obtain a large enough numerical database of panhead accelerations and interaction forces is described in Section 2. Section 3 describes the main features of the ANNs used in the study. Section 4 checks the accuracy of the different ANNs proposed, from simple classification problems, in which all the parameters are controlled, to more realistic problems in a laboratory environment. Some concluding remarks are given in Section 5.

2. Database

A large enough database is necessary to train and test ANNs. The first dataset was obtained by means of numerical simulations of the pantograph-catenary dynamic interaction, considering as many realistic features as possible. The second database was obtained from experimental tests on a real pantograph (see Section 4.4).

The pantograph-catenary interaction force depends on the catenary geometry, which can be affected by some installation errors [29]. Among them, the contact wire height is considered in the catenary models developed because it is the source of variability that most impact has on the interaction force. Additionally, some of the catenary models considered dropper faults (missing, broken, or slackened droppers) and severe contact wire wear. Curved track layouts and other sources of stochasticity, such as wind action or train speed inaccuracies, were not considered.

The catenary and pantograph models chosen to obtain the numerical database were defined according to the real stitched catenary described in EN-50318 [30]. As can be seen in Figure 2, it is composed of two catenary sections with spans of various lengths and number of droppers. These catenary sections (see the closed-up view in Figure 2) overlap each other to guarantee an uninterrupted power supply so that the pantograph interacts simultaneously with the contact wire of both catenary sections. To avoid boundary effects and the initial transient regime, we considered a length of 728.92 m with 13 spans, from the 8th mast of the first section (356.04 m) to the 10th mast of the second section (1084.96 m).

Figure 2: The nominal catenary model with two overlapped sections and the region of interest for the simulations. Closed-up view of the five overlapping spans.

Some features of the nominal catenary model were modified to create a set of different catenaries with enough variability. As previously mentioned, the catenary models were provided with realistic contact wire irregularity (see Section 2.1). The interaction of the catenary models with the pantograph was simulated at three different train speeds (200, 250 and 300 km/h). 100 nominal catenary models with irregular contact wire height (hereinafter referred to as Cat. #1) were created and simulated at the three speeds considered to obtain 300 data series. To simulate dropper faults such as slackened or broken droppers, four droppers were removed from Cat. #1 to create another 100 catenaries of the model labelled Cat. #2. With the same strategy, four other droppers were removed from Cat. #1 to create the 100 models for Cat. #3 and Cat. #4 (see Table 1). For example, code $D3-S1$ denotes a fault in the third dropper of the first span. When a dropper was removed from an overlapping span, the catenary section to which it belongs is also labelled "(1)" or "(2)" for sections 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1: Different sets of catenary models created to obtain the simulation database.

	Cat. #1	Cat. #2	Cat. #3	Cat. #4	Cat. #5
Dropper faults	No	$D3-S1$	$D2-S2$	$D4-S3$	No
		$D4-S5$	$D3-S6$	$D2-S7(1)$	
		$D4-S8$	$D4-S7(2)$	$D5-S9$	
		$D6-S12$	$D5-S11$	$D2-S13$	
Contact wire wear	No	No	No	No	Yes

In addition to the catenary models with dropper faults, Cat. #5 was composed of 100 catenary models with contact wire wear (see Section 2.2) from which 300 dynamic simulations were performed (100 at each of the three train speeds considered) so that a total of 1500 dynamic simulations were carried out from the 500 catenary models.

2.1. Catenary models with contact wire height irregularities

The Finite Element Method based on the Absolute Nodal Coordinate Formulation (ANCF) [31] was chosen to model the catenaries. Both the static equilibrium equations and the design constraints must be fulfilled to build a given catenary model. Contact wire height irregularities were included via design constraints by imposing a given height on each connection point between the contact wire with a dropper or steady arm. This problem, known as the initial configuration or the shape-finding problem, combines the static equilibrium and the design constraint equations to set up a non-linear system of equations in which the nodal coordinates and the undeformed element lengths are unknown. The reader is referred to [32] for further information on the statement of this specific problem.

We followed the procedure proposed in [33] to achieve a contact wire height that represents a realistic profile of an installed catenary. Some measurements of the contact wire height in different catenary sections were first collected. We then defined the error in height as the difference between the real measurement and the nominal value of the contact wire height at a given point. This height error was averaged over all the catenary sections measured and transformed into the frequency domain by means of the Discrete Fourier Transform. The power spectral density (PSD) of the height error, \mathbf{z}_{err} , can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Power spectral density of the contact wire height error.

To generate a catenary model with contact wire height irregularities of the same frequency content as the actual installed catenaries, we first related a random phase to each frequency and reconstructed a spatial signal with the same length as the catenary section by means of the Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform. The error values that matched the connection points between the contact wire with droppers and steady arms \mathbf{z}_{err} were then selected, added to the nominal contact wire height \mathbf{z}_0 , and imposed on the initial configuration problem. The contact wire height at the initial static equilibrium configuration is thus:

$$\mathbf{z}_{cw} = \mathbf{z}_{err} + \mathbf{z}_0 \quad (1)$$

An example of the contact wire height of three catenary models after applying the described procedure is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Three examples of catenary contact wires with realistic height irregularities.

After obtaining the initial catenary configuration, the pantograph-catenary dynamic simulation was executed by the fast simulation strategy proposed in [34]. For this, the catenary model was linearised with respect to the initial configuration position and non-linear dropper behaviour (transmitting only traction forces) was dealt with by external correction forces. We used a lumped-mass pantograph model and a penalty stiffness of $k_h = 50000$ N/m to couple both the catenary and pantograph models. The uplift force applied to the bottom mass of the pantograph model was tuned to fulfil the maximum mean contact force requirement specified in EN-50367 [35]. The time integration was carried out by the Newmark method using a time step of 1 ms.

2.2. Catenary model with contact wire wear

The sliding contact between the pantograph collectors and the catenary contact wire produces wear on both contact surfaces. In this work, we considered wear on the contact wire by modifying the contact wire height at which the contact takes place. Thus,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{cw} = \mathbf{z}_{cw} + \mathbf{z}_{wear} \quad (2)$$

in which \mathbf{z}_{cw} is obtained from Eq. (1) and \mathbf{z}_{wear} represents the height of the contact wire removed due to wear. To compute the amount of wear at each contact point, we used the heuristic model proposed in [36], which defines the normal wear rate as:

$$NWR = 2 \cdot \left[k_1 \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{I_c}{I_0} \right) \right)^{-\alpha} \left(\frac{F_c}{2F_0} \right)^\beta \frac{F_c}{2H} + k_2 \frac{R_c I_c^2}{Hv} (1 - u) + k_3 \frac{V_a I_c}{vH_m \rho} u \right] \quad (3)$$

The NWR represents the worn section and is given in mm^2 . This model differentiates three contributions to total wear: (i) mechanical wear due to friction, (ii) electrical wear due to the Joule effect, and (iii) wear produced by electrical arcs by lost contact. These three contributions to the contact wire wear are directly related to the three terms present in Eq. (3). A detailed description of all the parameters involved in the wear model is provided in [36]. We considered all the parameter values given in this reference except the current intensity, which is assumed to be constant $I_c = 300$ A. The total contact force, F_c , and the contact loss rate u also come from the dynamic simulations. Note that the contact force appears divided by two and the NWR is also scaled by this factor since the wear model is valid for the contact force of a single contact strip and an equal distribution of forces between the two contact strips was assumed. According to [36], the electrical contact resistance R_c for the contact between a copper contact wire and a graphite contact strip is given by:

$$R_c = 0.3276 - \frac{F_c}{2} 3.47 \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (4)$$

For high speeds at which the contact force can be high, Eq. (4) could lead to negative values. To avoid this issue, $R_c = 0.015 \Omega$ if $F_c > 180.17$ N, which is the minimum resistance value given in [37].

The procedure followed to perform a complete dynamic simulation, including the contact wire wear, was divided into the following four steps:

1. Generate a catenary model with contact wire irregularities and execute a dynamic simulation as detailed in Section 2.1. This will give the total nominal contact force F_c as the result.
2. Applying Eq. (3) to obtain the normal wear ratio or the worn area in each contact point of the simulation. This result must be multiplied by the number of pantograph passages NPP . In this particular case, we took $NPP = 5 \cdot 10^7$ to obtain a worn area of around 20% at some points in each of the two catenary sections considered.

3. Compute the worn height z_{wear} of the contact wire. For a circular contact wire cross-section of 120 mm^2 and radius R , such as that represented in Figure 5, the worn height due to the previously computed worn area is obtained from Eq. (5), in which the angle θ is first computed by solving the nonlinear Eq. (6).

$$z_{wear} = R\left(1 - \cos \frac{\theta}{2}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{R^2}{2}(\theta - \sin \theta) - NWR \cdot NPP = 0 \quad (6)$$

Figure 5: Contact wire circular cross-section with the worn area shadowed.

4. Solve an additional dynamic simulation but now considering the contact wire height given by Eq. (2) to compute the interaction force.

To illustrate the effect of considering wear in the contact wire, the contact wire height and the pantograph-catenary contact force of a given catenary section are plotted in Figure 6. Note that the worn catenary contact wire height is higher due to lower weight and presents irregularities due to wear. Regarding the dynamic interaction, the worn catenary has a higher contact force standard deviation with higher peaks and lower minima.

Figure 6: Unworn (solid line) and worn (dot-dashed line) contact wire height, z_{cw} and \tilde{z}_{cw} (upper plot), and pantograph-catenary contact force (bottom plot).

2.3. Data pre-processing

After performing 1500 dynamic simulations, we stored the contact force, the acceleration and the displacement of the upper mass of the pantograph model, which represent vertical panhead motion. These magnitudes were only stored for the catenary region of interest (see Figure 2). However, the kilometre points at which the data was taken do not match in all the simulations since they were run at three different speeds. To solve this problem, we kept the kilometre points of the highest speed simulations (300 km/h) since they provided the coarsest spatial discretisation. All the other results obtained from the simulations at lower speeds (200 and 250 km/h) were then linearly interpolated at the previously stored kilometre points.

The second pre-processing action consisted of dividing the entire signals into M samples, giving a total of $M_t = 1500 \times M$ data series, each of them containing N points (or features) and only information on a few meters of catenary instead of the entire region of interest. In this case, we chose $M = 10$, which implies $N = 875$.

The input data of the ANN are the pantograph collector acceleration and were stored in the columns of the $N \times M_t$ matrix \mathbf{x} . It is important for the accuracy of the model to standardize each sample, for which we applied to each row of matrix \mathbf{x} :

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i = \frac{\mathbf{x}_i - \mu(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\sigma(\mathbf{x}_i)} \quad \text{for} \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (7)$$

in which $\mu(\cdot)$ is the mean and $\sigma(\cdot)$ the standard deviation. A scheme of the whole pre-processing approach can be seen in Figure 7 for a pantograph acceleration signal obtained from a simulation in which the pantograph runs at 200 km/h. In this case, each simulation result is divided into $M = 10$ series of $N = 875$ points each.

Figure 7: Scheme of pantograph acceleration pre-processing obtained from a dynamic simulation run at 200 km/h and divided into $M = 10$ data series.

3. Artificial Neural Networks architecture

Among the different machine learning techniques, in this work we used the widely known Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) [38] due to their flexibility, computational efficiency and ability to handle heterogeneous and noisy data. The ANNs developed in this study were used for both classification and regression problems. While classification

networks return a probability of between 0 and 1 that an input belongs to a given group or class, regression networks return a predicted scalar value. We built 7 ANNs (see Table 2) using the MATLAB[®] Neural Network Toolbox functions [39]. All of these use the standardized pantograph collector acceleration as input values. The first four are classification networks designed to detect dropper faults, severe contact wire wear and classify each input sample by the power supply quality quantified by the standard deviation of the interaction force. The last three are regression networks to predict the standard deviation, minimum and maximum of the pantograph-catenary contact force, which can be considered indicators of the current collection quality.

Table 2: Main features of the seven ANNs proposed in this work.

	Description	Output	Type
ANN#1	Detection of dropper faults	$y_1 =$ Probability of no dropper faults $y_2 =$ Probability of dropper faults	Class.
ANN#2	Detection of severe CW wear	$y_1 =$ Probability of unworn CW $y_2 =$ Probability of worn contact wire	Class.
ANN#12	Detection of severe CW wear and dropper faults	$y_1 =$ Probability of non-defective catenary $y_2 =$ Probability of worn contact wire $y_3 =$ Probability of dropper faults	Class.
ANN#3	Detection of bad contact quality	$y_1 =$ Probability of $\sigma(F_c) \in [0, 15]$ N $y_2 =$ Probability of $\sigma(F_c) \in [15, 30]$ N $y_3 =$ Probability of $\sigma(F_c) > 30$ N	Class.
ANN#4	Prediction of $\sigma(F_c)$	$y = \sigma^*(F_c)$	Regr.
ANN#5	Prediction of $\min(F_c)$	$y = \min^*(F_c)$	Regr.
ANN#6	Prediction of $\max(F_c)$	$y = \max^*(F_c)$	Regr.

As a common rule of thumb for regression networks, if the input layer considers N features, we set two hidden layers, the first with $N/2$ neurons and the second with $N/4$ neurons. The size of the ANNs output layers can be seen in the fourth column in Table 2. For the activation functions, we followed the usual recommendation for using the rectified linear activation function (ReLU) for regression networks. For classification problems, we only used one $N/2$ -size hidden layer. A hyperbolic tangent was selected as the activation function for the hidden layer, while the output layer uses a softmax function that returns the posterior probabilities of belonging to each of the possible k classes.

After defining the ANN architecture and parameters, the network must be trained. This consists of finding the weights \mathbf{w} and biases \mathbf{b} that minimize a given cost function. For regression ANNs, this cost function is composed of the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the predicted values \mathbf{y}^* and the target values \mathbf{y} and an L2 regularization term whose strength is controlled by the parameter λ , which was set to 0.1. When classifying neural networks for k classes, the cost function to be minimized during the training process is the Cross-Entropy loss function and also contains the L2 regularization term:

$$L = - \sum_{i=1}^k y_i \log y_i^* + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^{N_w} w_j^2 \quad (8)$$

in which y_i is the truth label, which can be either 0 or 1, and y_i^* is the predicted probability for the i -th class and N_w is the number of weights. The algorithm selected to solve the minimization problems and thus to train the ANN is the Scaled Conjugate Gradient Backpropagation algorithm [40]. When the magnitude of the gradients of the cost function with respect to the weights and the biases are below 10^{-3} , the training process stops. In practice, we used all the built-in MATLAB functions of the Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox to create, train and test the ANNs. All the hyperparameters that define the ANNs proposed (number of hidden layers, layers size, activation function, regularisation strength, ...) were those that, after a thorough seek, provided the best regression and classification results.

4. Numerical results

4.1. Performance of the trained ANNs

This section describes the analysis of the performance of the trained ANNs. The results were obtained with all the parameter values defined in Sections 2 and 3. 70% of the input samples of each ANN were used for training and the remaining 30% for validation purposes.

For ANN#1 we had a total of 12000 samples, composed of the $M = 10$ subdivisions of each of the 100 simulations of Cat.#1, Cat.#2, Cat.#3 and Cat.#4 at three different speeds. The ANN#1 validation results are shown in Figure 8 by means of a confusion chart. It can be seen that the hit rate is extremely high since only 0.1% of the samples with no dropper faults are catalogued as faulty, while 0.3% of the samples with dropper faults are categorized as non-fault samples. This indicates an excellent performance in detecting dropper faults from the pantograph collector vertical acceleration.

Figure 8: Confusion chart of the ANN#1 validation for detection of dropper faults.

ANN#2 is devoted to detecting severe wear in the catenary contact wire. In this case, the input data were generated from Cat.#1 and Cat.#5, leading to 6000 acceleration samples, of which 4200 were used to train ANN#2 and 1800 to test it. As shown in Figure 9, severe contact wire wear can be accurately detected from panhead vertical acceleration.

Figure 9: Confusion chart of the ANN#2 validation for detection of contact wire severe wear.

It is important to emphasise that ANN#1 and ANN#2 were trained with samples obtained from catenaries that only considered one type of defect, i.e. dropper faults in ANN#1 and contact wire wear in ANN#2. However, in a more realistic scenario, both defects can appear simultaneously. To assess the performance of these two ANNs in this case, ANN#1 was tested with samples from worn catenaries (Cat. #5 in Table.1) and ANN#2 with samples from catenaries with dropper faults (Cat. #2, Cat. #3 and Cat. #4 in Table.1). ANN#1 provided a hit rate of 83.4%, which means that it confused worn contact wire samples with defective dropper samples in 16.6% of the cases. ANN#2's misclassification rate was around 9%.

A practical solution to improve classification success when both defects are present is to create a new ANN (ANN#12 in Table 2) trained with the five sets of samples described in Table 1 to discern between non-faulty, worn and faulty dropper samples. The confusion chart in Figure 10 shows ANN#12's excellent accuracy in identifying each type of defect.

Figure 10: Confusion chart of the ANN#12 validation for detection of severe contact wire wear and dropper faults.

ANN#3 classified each sample in terms of the $\sigma(F_c)$, which is the usual indicator of current collection performance. In this case, we selected the same 12000 samples as in ANN#1. Specifically, ANN#3 was trained to classify the

pantograph acceleration samples into three categories: i) $\sigma(F_c) < 15$ N, ii) $15 \text{ N} \leq \sigma(F_c) \leq 30$ N and iii) $\sigma(F_c) > 30$ N. Figure 11 shows the confusion chart with the percentages of the 3600 validation samples that quantify the performance of ANN#3. As can be seen, the largest error in classifying these samples is around 9%, while a given misclassified sample is labelled as only one greater or lower class, i.e. any sample with $\sigma(F_c) \geq 30$ N is classified as having $\sigma(F_c) < 15$ N and vice versa. In light of these results, using an ANN is a good option to detect catenary sections with abnormal $\sigma(F_c)$ from panhead acceleration.

Figure 11: Confusion chart of the ANN#3 validation for classification of $\sigma(F_c)$.

To deeply analyse the results of ANN#3, $\sigma(F_c)$ of the same validation samples are plotted in Figure 12 in which the blue markers in are the samples properly classified, whilst the red markers are the misclassified samples. They represent only 6.33% of the 3600 validation samples. It is important to note that the most misclassified samples (red markers in Figure 12) have $\sigma(F_c)$ near the bound values of the three categories. These results were expected since those samples with $\sigma(F_c) \approx 15$ N or $\sigma(F_c) \approx 30$ N are more prone to be classified in the range to which they do not belong.

Figure 12: $\sigma(F_c)$ of the 3600 samples used to validate ANN#3. Properly classified samples (blue markers) and misclassified samples (red markers).

ANN#4, ANN#5 and ANN#6 are regression networks to predict $\sigma(F_c)$, $\min(F_c)$ and $\max(F_c)$, respectively, from the vertical acceleration of the pantograph collector. All three ANNs were trained with 8400 samples and further validated with the remaining 3600 acceleration samples, as in ANN#1 and ANN#3. The validation is shown in Figure 13, in which the predicted values given by the ANNs are plotted versus the true values. The solid line indicates the correct prediction, while the dashed and the dash-dotted lines denote a 10% and a 20% prediction error, respectively.

Figure 13: True values versus predicted values of $\sigma(F_c)$, $\max(F_c)$ and $\min(F_c)$ given by regression ANN#4, ANN#5 and ANN#6 respectively from left to right.

The percentage of validation samples with a prediction error lower than 5, 10 and 20% and the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) are given in Table 3. This is a more challenging problem but, even so, more than 93% of the tested samples have less than 5% prediction accuracy for ANN#4 and ANN#5. Although ANN#6 exhibits the poorest prediction accuracy, in almost 95% of the cases the minimum value of the contact force is predicted with an error of less than 10%. The ANN#6's lower prediction accuracy could be due to the fact that it consists of a highly localized feature and there are some values of F_c near the minimum in a given sample.

Table 3: Statistics of $\sigma(F_c)$ predicted by ANN#4, ANN#5 and ANN#6.

Prediction error	<5% [%]	<10% [%]	<20% [%]	RMSE [N]
ANN#4	93.03	99.36	100	0.49
ANN#5	94.67	99.72	100	5.23
ANN#6	76.86	94.67	99.36	4.57

4.2. Other operating conditions

The six ANNs analysed in this work showed excellent performance when applied to pantograph acceleration test signals from the original simulation database. However, as it was important to confirm whether these ANNs can make accurate predictions from signals obtained from operating conditions other than those used to obtain the training data, we selected ANN#4 for comparison purposes.

The first case analysed consisted of acceleration signals obtained from simulated pantograph-catenary dynamic interactions, with different catenary and/or pantograph models from those used to generate the database (see Section 2). In this scenario, ANN#4 showed a very poor power of generalization, predicting unreal $\sigma(F_c)$ values, which indicates that training ANNs with data collected from the catenary-pantograph couple to which it will be applied is crucial to obtain accurate predictions.

ANN#4 accuracy was also tested with pantograph accelerations from simulations with train speeds other than those considered in the training set. As mentioned in Section 2, the database was compiled with simulations run at 200, 250, and 300 km/h. Figure 14 shows the predicted $\sigma(F_c)$ versus true values for 20 samples obtained at 225 km/h and another 20 at 275 km/h (blue dots). Although ANN#4 tends to greatly overestimate the true $\sigma(F_c)$, the prediction accuracy improved considerably with a new ANN (ANN#4*) trained with the same number of samples obtained by simulations at $v \in [200,210,\dots,300]$ km/h (red dots in Figure 14).

Figure 14: Comparison of ANN#4 (blue dots) and ANN#4* (red dots) $\sigma(F_c)$ predictions for the 40 samples obtained at running speeds of 225 and 275 km/h.

Given this scenario, we propose the following two alternatives:

- a) Since high-speed trains travel at or close to their nominal speed most of the time, a practical solution is to define different ANNs for the speeds considered. To illustrate this strategy, 300 km/h was considered the nominal speed to train ANN#4a with 2400 acceleration samples obtained at pantograph speeds of 295, 300 and 305 km/h. 600 samples at 297 and 302 km/h were then used for validation purposes (Fig. 15(a)).

- b) When a single ANN is meant to make predictions for a wider range of train speeds, we propose training ANN#4b with acceleration samples obtained at random velocities within the specified range. For example, for $v \in [250,300]$ km/h, Fig. 15(b) shows the 600 predictions from the ANN#4b validation set, which was also trained with 2400 acceleration samples.

Figure 15: Prediction of $\sigma(F_c)$ with (a) ANN#4a trained at three speeds in a narrow speed range and (b) ANN#4b trained at random speeds in a wide speed range.

Although the percentages shown in the two first rows of Table 4 are good and denote a reasonably similar prediction accuracy of these two strategies, the performance of Option b) is actually higher because the prediction range of $\sigma(F_c)$ is considerably wider.

Table 4: Statistics of $\sigma(F_c)$ predicted by ANN#4a, ANN#4b and ANN#4x.

Prediction error	<5% [%]	<10% [%]	<20% [%]	RMSE [N]
ANN#4a	89.35	98.00	100	0.82
ANN#4b	91.78	99.67	100	0.75
ANN#4x	71.56	94.44	99.78	1.32

4.3. Using displacements instead of accelerations as ANN input

Using panhead vertical displacement instead of acceleration signals implies using, from a practical point of view, a laser sensor or similar. We proposed two options of using the measured (in this case simulated) pantograph displacements: i) computing the accelerations via a numerical differentiation scheme (e.g. central differences) and using these computed acceleration samples to train the ANN, and ii) training the ANN directly with the displacement samples. To validate these two options, a comparison of the prediction accuracy on the same validation set is shown in Figure 16 for the ANN trained with the acceleration computed from pantograph vertical displacement (Fig. 16(a)) and the ANN trained directly by the simulated pantograph vertical displacement (Fig. 16(a)). As can be seen, the first option leads to a much better prediction accuracy, similar to that of ANN#4 (see Fig. 13) with an RMSE of 0.5 N, while the second option has poorer prediction power with an RMSE of 1.94 N. However, if this approach needs to be applied to real measured displacements, it is important to filter them to 20 Hz before applying the differentiation

scheme to reduce the possible numerical artifacts in the resulting acceleration, due to the presence of measurement noise in the acquired displacements.

Figure 16: Prediction of $\sigma(F_c)$ by ANNs trained with: (a) accelerations computed from displacements, and (b) the simulation displacement results.

4.4. Application to experimental measures from a pantograph test bench

To get closer to a real scenario, the proposed method was tested with acceleration samples measured on a DSA-380 pantograph. The collector-head was excited by a linear motor on the pantograph test bench described in [28]. As shown in Fig. 17, this linear motor followed the vertical displacement of the pantograph collector-head obtained from purely numerical simulations and enforced the same displacement at the midpoint of each contact strip. The pantograph-catenary contact force and the contact strips' vertical acceleration were synchronously measured by means of two load cells and two accelerometers (see the zoomed-in view in Fig. 17). The lateral movement of the actuator to reproduce catenary stagger was not considered in the tests. This feature would cause a rolling motion of the collector head, which barely affects the contact force. In fact, Standard EN-50317 also neglects the effect of the collector head roll motion since it averages the two acceleration measures on each end of the contact strip. There is thus no difference between using a single accelerometer at the centre of each contact strip and using two accelerometers at both ends of each contact strip and then taking the average acceleration.

Figure 17: Photo of the pantograph test bench and zoomed-in view of sensors used to measure acceleration and interaction force on a contact strip with an example of the computed vertical displacement imposed by the linear motor.

The procedure proposed in this paper was applied to these measured signals to train and validate an ANN to predict the standard deviation of the interaction force. The mean of both acceleration measures was used as the input to train ANN#4x, while the standard deviation of the sum of both measured forces was the output used for training.

As the example of validating the proposed approach with experimental measures, we selected Alternative b) described in Section 4.2, which consisted of training the ANN with acceleration samples obtained at random train speeds. With the numerical simulations used to obtain Fig. 15(b), 300 tests were performed on the test bench to measure both the acceleration and interaction force. Each measured signal was resampled and divided into 10 samples, as described in Section 2.3. The predictions obtained from 600 validation samples after training ANN#4x are shown in Fig. 18.

Figure 18: True of $\sigma(F_c)$ values versus the predicted values given by regression ANN#4x from samples obtained at random train speeds between 250 and 300 km/h.

As shown in Table 4, unlike its numerical counterpart ANN#4b, ANN#4x offers poorer $\sigma(F_c)$ prediction accuracy

since only 72% of the samples had less than 5% prediction error. However, in almost 95% of the cases the prediction error obtained was less than 10% and the RMSE of the 600 predictions was approximately 1.3 N. These results confirm that the proposed approach is still applicable to experimentally measured signals with satisfactory predictions, even though it loses a certain amount of accuracy compared to the purely numerical scenario.

5. Conclusions

The results obtained show the potential of Artificial Neural Networks as an efficient method of monitoring the health status and predicting current collection quality indicators in railway catenaries from pantograph accelerations. This will allow a single accelerometer to be used on a conventional pantograph for efficient and low-cost catenary condition monitoring in real time instead of resorting to instrumented pantographs mounted on inspection vehicles.

To correctly set the parameters that govern the proposed approach, it was applied first to simple classification problems, in which ANNs were trained and tested with data obtained from thousands of numerical simulations to detect broken or slackened droppers and severe contact wire wear. More challenging problems aimed at classifying the standard deviation of the interaction force in certain ranges and predicting the interaction force maximum, minimum, and standard deviation values were then analysed. The results obtained show a classification and prediction accuracy above 90%. Even when the method was applied to experimental data obtained from a pantograph test bench, the same level of accuracy was obtained, which confirms its potential for analysing on-track measured data.

The proposed method also presents some limitations. On the one hand, the ANNs showed a very poor power of generalization when applied to acceleration signals obtained from catenary and/or pantograph models other than those used to train them. On the other hand, when the accelerations were measured at different train speeds, they must be synchronised at the same kilometric points by applying the resampling strategy described in Section 2.3 to avoid reducing their prediction accuracy. In practice, this means that when applying this method to on-track data it is crucial to have a precise measure of the train speed. It is also important to highlight that if the pantograph collector displacement were to be used instead of the acceleration, the proposed method could lead to $\sigma(F_c)$ predictions with more than a 20% error.

In this work we confirmed the well-known ANNs' bad power of generalisation. However, if the training data and hyperparameters are properly selected they are good at interpolating. This paper also shows that accurate σF_c predictions can be made from experimental data, provided that the test conditions are suitably controlled in the laboratory. Future research will be focused on how to perform these tests so that trained ANNs can work with on-track measured data.

Although the numerical simulations used in this work considered realistic variability in the contact wire height and different train speeds, and the experimental tests also included measurement noise in the acquired accelerations and forces, other sources of variability, such as environmental conditions (wind, temperature, etc.) or a curved track layout were not included and need to be dealt with in further studies.

This study is an intermediate step between pure numerical assessment and on-track data application, which contributes to the ongoing efforts to improve the safety, reliability and efficiency of high-speed train operations and provides valuable insights into using ANNs for fault detection and diagnosis in the pantograph-catenary system.

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References

- [1] F. Kiessling, R. Puschmann, A. Schmieder, E. Schneider, Contact lines for electric railways: planning, design, implementation, maintenance, John Wiley & Sons, 2018.
- [2] F. Alkam, T. Lahmer, Eigenfrequency-based Bayesian approach for damage identification in catenary poles, *Infrastructures* 6 (4) (2021) 57.
- [3] D. Efanov, D. Sedykh, G. Osadchy, D. Barch, Permanent monitoring of railway overhead catenary poles inclination, in: 2017 IEEE East-West Design & Test Symposium (EWDTS), IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–5.
- [4] W. Liu, Z. Liu, A. Núñez, L. Wang, K. Liu, Y. Lyu, H. Wang, Multi-objective performance evaluation of the detection of catenary support components using DCNNs, *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 51 (9) (2018) 98–105.
- [5] J. Chen, Z. Liu, H. Wang, A. Nunez, Z. Han, Automatic defect detection of fasteners on the catenary support device using deep convolutional neural network, *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 67 (2) (2017) 257–269.
- [6] J. Zhong, Z. Liu, H. Wang, W. Liu, C. Yang, Z. Han, A. Núñez, A looseness detection method for railway catenary fasteners based on reinforcement learning refined localization, *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 70 (2021) 1–13.
- [7] J. Zhou, Z. Han, L. Wang, A steady arm slope detection method based on 3D point cloud segmentation, in: 2018 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Image, Vision and Computing (ICIVC), IEEE, 2018, pp. 278–282.
- [8] G. Karaduman, E. Akin, A new approach based on predictive maintenance using the fuzzy classifier in pantograph-catenary systems, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* (2020).
- [9] D. He, H. Wang, J. Miao, Research on condition monitoring system of high speed railway catenary based on image processing, *Journal of Measurements in Engineering* 4 (1) (2016) 23–31.
- [10] L. Chang, X. Pan, Z. Fu, D. Li, S. Liu, G. Zhang, Robust online dynamic detection method for PAC operational status of high-speed trains based on key point positioning, *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 71 (2022) 1–14.
- [11] D. Zhang, S. Gao, L. Yu, G. Kang, D. Zhan, X. Wei, A robust pantograph–catenary interaction condition monitoring method based on deep convolutional network, *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 69 (5) (2019) 1920–1929.
- [12] E. Karakose, M. T. Gencoglu, M. Karakose, I. Aydin, E. Akin, A new experimental approach using image processing-based tracking for an efficient fault diagnosis in pantograph–catenary systems, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 13 (2) (2016) 635–643.
- [13] S. Gao, Automatic detection and monitoring system of pantograph–catenary in China’s high-speed railways, *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 70 (2020) 1–12.
- [14] H. Wang, A. Núñez, Z. Liu, D. Zhang, R. Dollevoet, A Bayesian network approach for condition monitoring of high-speed railway catenaries, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 21 (10) (2019) 4037–4051.
- [15] H. Wang, Unsupervised anomaly detection in railway catenary condition monitoring using autoencoders, in: *IECON 2020 The 46th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, IEEE, 2020, pp. 2636–2641.
- [16] S. Borromeo López, Algoritmos de optimización para la adquisición y procesamiento de imágenes capturadas con cámaras CCD lineales: aplicación a los sistemas de medida del desgaste hilo de contacto en las líneas electrificadas de ferrocarril, Ph.D. thesis, Industriales (2004).
- [17] G. Karaduman, E. Akin, A deep learning based method for detecting of wear on the current collector strips’ surfaces of the pantograph in railways, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 183799–183812.
- [18] A. Shing, F. Miu, Predicting the contact wire wear of a railway system using ANN, in: *CORE 2012, Rail-the core of integrated transport, conference on railway engineering*, Perth, Western Australia, 7–10 September 2012, 2012.
- [19] S. Huang, Y. Zhai, M. Zhang, X. Hou, Arc detection and recognition in pantograph–catenary system based on convolutional neural network, *Information Sciences* 501 (2019) 363–376.
- [20] Y. Luo, Q. Yang, S. Liu, Novel vision-based abnormal behavior localization of pantograph–catenary for high-speed trains, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 180935–180946.
- [21] S. Kusumi, T. Fukutani, K. Nezu, Diagnosis of overhead contact line based on contact force, *Quarterly Report of RTRI* 47 (1) (2006) 39–45.
- [22] M. Boccione, G. Bucca, A. Collina, L. Comolli, Pantograph–catenary monitoring by means of fibre Bragg grating sensors: Results from tests in an underground line, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 41 (1–2) (2013) 226–238.
- [23] EN 50317, Railway applications. Current collection systems. Requirements for and validation of measurements of the dynamic interaction between pantograph and overhead contact line, European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (2012).
- [24] S. Liu, Y. Wei, Y. Yin, T. Feng, J. Lin, Structural health monitoring method of pantograph–catenary system based on strain response inversion, *Frontiers in Physics* 9 (2021) 691510.
- [25] A. Collina, F. Fossati, M. Papi, F. Resta, Impact of overhead line irregularity on current collection and diagnostics based on the measurement of pantograph dynamics, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit* 221 (4) (2007) 547–559.
- [26] H. Wang, Z. Liu, A. Núñez, R. Dollevoet, Identification of the catenary structure wavelength using pantograph head acceleration measurements, in: 2017 IEEE International Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference (I2MTC), IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [27] M. Carnevale, A. Collina, Processing of collector acceleration data for condition-based monitoring of overhead lines, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit* 230 (2) (2016) 472–485.
- [28] A. Correcher, C. Ricolfe-Viala, M. Tur, S. Gregori, M. Salvador-Muñoz, F. J. Fuenmayor, J. Gil, A. M. Pedrosa, Hardware-in-the-loop test bench for simulation of catenary–pantograph interaction (CPI) with linear camera measurement, *Sensors* 23 (4) (2023) 1773.
- [29] S. Gregori, M. Tur, J. Tarancón, F. Fuenmayor, Stochastic monte carlo simulations of the pantograph–catenary dynamic interaction to allow for uncertainties introduced during catenary installation, *Vehicle System Dynamics* 57 (4) (2019) 471–492.
- [30] EN 50318, Railway applications. Current collection systems. Validation of simulation of the dynamic interaction between pantograph and overhead contact line, European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (2018).
- [31] M. Berzeri, A. Shabana, Development of simple models for the elastic forces in the absolute nodal co-ordinate formulation, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 235 (4) (2000) 539–565.
- [32] M. Tur, E. García, L. Baeza, F. Fuenmayor, A 3D absolute nodal coordinate finite element model to compute the initial configuration of a railway catenary, *Engineering Structures* 71 (2014) 234–243.

- [33] O. Vo Van, J.-P. Massat, C. Laurent, E. Balmes, Introduction of variability into pantograph–catenary dynamic simulations, *Vehicle system dynamics* 52 (10) (2014) 1254–1269.
- [34] S. Gregori, M. Tur, E. Nadal, J. Aguado, F. Fuenmayor, F. Chinesta, Fast simulation of the pantograph–catenary dynamic interaction, *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design* 129 (2017) 1–13.
- [35] EN 50367, Railway applications. Current collection systems. Technical criteria for the interaction between pantograph and overhead line, European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (2012).
- [36] S. Derosa, P. Navik, A. Collina, G. Bucca, A. Ronnquist, A heuristic wear model for the contact strip and contact wire in pantograph–catenary interaction for railway operations under 15 kV 16.67 Hz AC systems, *Wear* 456 (2020) 203401.
- [37] G. Bucca, A. Collina, R. Manigrasso, F. Mapelli, D. Tarsitano, Analysis of electrical interferences related to the current collection quality in pantograph–catenary interaction, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit* 225 (5) (2011) 483–500.
- [38] M. A. Nielsen, *Neural networks and deep learning*, Vol. 25, Determination press San Francisco, CA, USA, 2015.
- [39] M. Hudson, M. Hagan, H. Demuth, *Neural Network Toolbox, User’s Guide*, MATLAB, Mathworks (2014).
- [40] M. F. Moller, A scaled conjugate gradient algorithm for fast supervised learning, *Neural networks* 6 (4) (1993) 525–533.